

A Deterministic Scheduler for Hybrid Wired and Wireless Network Resources over Cloud-Edge Continuum Computing Platform

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In the current era of the fifth-generation (5G) network technology, characterized by ultra-low latency networks, there is an anticipation that 5G will provide robust support for emerging digital twin applications requiring time-sensitive traffic management [1]. These applications, traversing interdisciplinary domains such as factory automation, autonomous vehicles, remote medicine, and immersive environments, highlight the diverse and extensive impact of cutting-edge 5G networks. The handling of time-sensitive traffic in these scenarios involves strict observance of quality-of-service (QoS) requirements, specifically addressing objectives such as delay, reliability, and jitter [2]. It is noteworthy that these QoS requirements diverge from the goals of previous network generations, which were primarily focused on enhancing data rates.

Achieving ultra-low latency in 5G networks involves implementing sophisticated techniques, including seamless integration of cloud and edge resources. By deploying computing resources closer to the network edge and seamlessly integrating cloud services, the distance data needs to travel is minimized, resulting in significantly reduced latency [3]. For instance, in autonomous vehicles, edge computing allows real-time decision-making at the vehicle level, improving response times for critical tasks like collision avoidance. Rather than transmitting data directly to the cloud, we leverage an edge server to offload certain tasks, resulting in faster response times delivered directly to the edge device and minimizing latency. This technique indicates how installing computing resources contributes to achieving ultra-low latency, enhancing the overall performance of 5G networks.

However, deploying additional computing resources proves insufficient due to the allocation and scheduling of limited network resources. Therefore, an efficient scheduling approach for network resources becomes imperative to ensure the allocation of adequate network resources for each computing resource, both on the edge and cloud sides, all within the designated time constraints. Through advanced scheduling algorithms, network can prioritize and allocate resources efficiently, ensuring that time-sensitive tasks, like those in autonomous systems, receive immediate attention. The network scheduling is essential for mitigating transmission delays, crucially addressing the diverse QoS requirements.

Existing network resource schedulers, such as proportional fair, round-robin, earliest-deadline-first, and maximum throughput, lack a specific focus on addressing the needs of time-sensitive traffic. This insufficiency serves as our motivation to design a novel network scheduling approach tailored to meet QoS requirements for time-sensitive traffic in 5G networks, encompassing both wired and wireless connections. While there have been advanced in developing schedulers for time-sensitive traffic in wired networks through the time-sensitive networking (TSN) standardization [4], there remains a critical space in addressing similar requirements for wireless connections. Specht et al. [5] advanced this field with an urgency-based scheduler that allocates hard real-time data flows to queues, impacting latencies significantly.

Since ultra-reliability and low latency (URLLC) in 5G networks facilitates performance levels related to wireless networks, thereby unlocking new possibilities for diverse applications. Khoshnevisan et al. designed of end-to-end 5G wireless networks specifically tailored for industrial factory automation [6]. Moreover, Gintor et al. analyzed the technical challenges for implement time-sensitive traffic over wireless connection in 5G [7]. Their work proposed a simulator to investigate the impact and defining QoS for the system. Despite these advancements, there is currently a lack of an optimal scheduler for hybrid wired and wireless network resources.

Therefore, we propose the development of a deterministic scheduler tailored for hybrid wired and wireless network resources on a cloud-edge continuum computing platform as shown in Fig. 1. This scheduler leverages 5G network technology, where $a^x(t)$ denotes the action on resource x at time t , $s^x(t)$ represents the state of network resource x at time t , and $r^x(t)$ is the reward from resource x at time t for action $a^x(t)$ in state $s^x(t)$. The set $\tau^x(t)$ includes transitions, pairing $s^x(t)$ and $a^x(t)$ up to time t . Parameters μ and Q correspond to the actor and critic models. The scheduling problem in hybrid wired and wireless networks can be framed as an optimal control problem within a Markov Decision Process (MDP), making it suitable for addressing with reinforcement learning [8]. Three challenges can be identified across phases including problem formulation, training algorithm, and online implementation.

Fig. 1. The architecture of proposed deterministic scheduler for hybrid wired and wireless network resources over cloud-edge continuum computing platform

We will thoroughly investigate and address these issues in our proposed scheduler. Recently, actor-critic deep reinforcement learning algorithms have emerged to tackle these challenges. These algorithms involve two neural networks approximating the policy and the long-term reward, respectively [9]. In cases where the optimal policy is deterministic, as is often the case in optimal control problems, these algorithms transform into deep deterministic policy gradient (DDPG) methods [10]. Leveraging the DDPG concept, we aim to enhance and apply it to efficiently schedule network resources.

As part of our future work, we aim to create a network scheduler for both wired and wireless networks. For the wireless part, we will focus on considering what each user or device needs in QoS. Similarly, when scheduling wired connections from the cloud, we will factor in QoS from network providers or edge servers. The ultimate goal is to blend these wired and wireless networks into a single scheduler that ensures applications receive the service quality they need. This combined scheduler will play a key role in smoothly transmitting time-sensitive data from edge devices to the cloud.

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